

INFLUENCE OF DESTRUCTIVE IDEAS AND GROUPS ON YOUNG PEOPLE AS A SOCIAL-PSYCHOLOGICAL PROBLEM

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Abstract. *The article presents the results of research conducted by the authors on the possible impact of destructive ideas and groups on the security of the individual, the state, and society, formation of anti-manipulative, assertive behavior in young people, formation of the culture of information consumption, and conclusions and practical suggestions based on them.*

Keywords: *destructive behavior, destructive consciousness, destructiveness, manipulation, security, youth, assertiveness, personality values, communication, aggression.*

One of the biggest problems facing the world community today is the threat of religious extremism and terrorism, which worries all mankind. These threats, empowered by means of globalization, are increasing day by day. In many countries and regions of the world, hundreds of thousands of people are killed in bloody conflicts due to religious extremism and terrorism. As a result, the need to carry out socio-psychological, preventive work against these evils in order to ensure peace is becoming more and more important.

This institution is the largest, legal body and legitimate foundation of a number of hujatlar Uzbekistan Presidential Republic 2017 Il July 5 "If the State policy of samaradorligin oshirish and Uzbekistan If the functional Union of Kulyab expanded force" decree of Belgilangan and the competence of the skillful and skillful spirit assistance, professional development, 2019 3rd pilot project "concrete potential and the development of human resources skills, the preparation of the tizimin node, the organization of this event is a long-term measure", Uzbekistan The Republic of Uzbekistan closed its meeting "2022-2023 yilda Uzbekistan The Republic of Uzbekistan on policy actions consistent with the guiding principles", Uzbekistan the Republic of Tajikistan 2019 June 7, 472-dream "Psychology is prepared for training and improving the activities of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan". During the meeting, the following issues were discussed: "During the conversation, the parties discussed issues and prospects for cooperation, as well as issues related to compliance with regulatory legal norms and regulatory norms. According to the press service of the President of the Republic of Tajikistan Emomali Rahmon, during the meeting the parties discussed issues of cooperation between Tajikistan and Tajikistan, as well as issues of cooperation between Tajikistan and China.

The issue of destructive behavior, destructive consciousness, destructive religious ideas is not only a topical issue of psychology, but also one of the most topical issues of pedagogy, sociology, jurisprudence, religion. In essence, the problem of destructive religious ideas is the subject of interdisciplinary research. Although fundamental research has been carried out in many areas on this issue, the need for research related to its psychological aspects is extremely high. Because nowadays, things like influencing the human mind, manipulating it, inviting young people to destructive ideas are accelerating on a global scale. Therefore, it is very important to review the scientific approaches created in connection with destructive behavior, destructive consciousness, destructive religious ideas and their influence on the minds of young people, and to integrate new psychological knowledge into them.

Psychological scientists of the CIS countries have created a unique school in issues such as deviance and its origins, the psychology of difficult-to-educate youth, psychocorrection of juvenile criminal behavior, among them F.E. Vasilyuk, P.M. Granovskaya, A.I. Demyanov, S.I. Ivanenko, M. P. Mchedlov, B. C. Mukhina conducted research on religiosity, religious belief and its influence on human behavior, among them R. V. Antonikov, U. V. Gladkova, O. M. Ilnitskaya, A. O. Medvedeva, Scientists such as D.A.Baryshev, O.D.Germanovskaya have conducted unique research on issues such as destructive behavior and its motives, causes of destructive behavior in adolescents, diagnosis of destructive behavior and its prevention.

In the years of independence, Uzbek historians, sociologists, philosophers, political scientists A. Begmatov, A. Zakurlaev, A. Yunusov, B. Irisov, B. Ochilova, G. Tulenova, Z. Husniddinov, I. Kudryavtsev, M. Bekmurodov, M. Lafasov, M. Khadjieva, M. Yuldashev, N. Safarova, R. Toshkuvatova, S. Tuychieva, K. Kuronboev, Q. Nazarov et al. conducted research. E.G. Goziev, Sh.R. Barotov, A.M. Jabborov from a number of psychologists in the psychology of our country on such issues as destructive behavior and its causes, psychology of criminal behavior, young people with delinquent behavior, psychological aspects of understanding religious texts, psychological characteristics of young people who are difficult to educate , B.M. Umarov, Z.T. Nishanova, U.D. Kadirov, G.Q. Tolaganova, N.G. Kamilova, B.N. Sirliev, I.M. Hakimova, D.Sh. Barotova, M It can be found in the scientific researches of Kh. Akhmedova, A. G. Abdukakhharova and A. M. Jabbar. Although this group of scientists has created a unique methodology for criminal behavior, deviant behavior and psychological methods of its elimination, no research has been conducted on psychological ways of protecting teenagers from destructive religious ideas. From this point of view, this dissertation research work on the topic of socio-psychological features of protecting teenagers from destructive religious ideas is considered to be a very relevant work in terms of implementation.

The concept of "ideological immunity" (Latin *immunitatis* - freedom from something) is a historical phenomenon, a system that serves to protect an individual, social group, nation, society from various harmful ideological influences.

In psychology, certain methods are used to determine the structure of the direction of personal values and to research them from a scientific and practical point of view. It is known that the direction of personal values is a socio-psychological basis, on the basis of which a person's character, consciousness and self-awareness are formed. Currently, the most widely used methodology for determining the direction of personal values was developed by Milton Rokich, an American psychologist of Polish nationality³. The system of value direction shows a person's attitude towards himself, the environment, and other people, and plays an important role in studying the fundamentals that make up personal worldview, motivation of life activity, clarifying the "I" concept, researching beliefs, worldview, and profession.

Young people studying in comprehensive schools, academic lyceums and colleges are not sufficiently formed of religious knowledge. In particular, due to the lack of personnel with religious knowledge in educational institutions, the teaching of these subjects is assigned to non-specialist pedagogues. As a result of this, there are cases of religious illiteracy, misinterpretation of religion and influence of various destructive ideas among young people. At the same time, these shortcomings are also encountered in the passing of the subject of "national idea", which is one of the main subjects for young people to find their place in life and to be educated as a perfect person. As a result, unprofessional pedagogues fail to take into account the age characteristics of students

and fill their ideological gaps. And this remains one of the main factors in the influence of young people under the influence of destructive ideas.

The representatives of the field say that the characteristics of the student were not taken into account in the creation of textbooks included in the national concept. Further problems arise due to the fact that students do not understand the essence of the topics covered while reading the textbooks. This is one of the main factors in the lack of immunity to destructive ideas among our people and their obsession with various foreign ideas.

Protecting young people from crime, harmful vices, extremist ideas and the influence of "popular culture" becomes even more important in today's globalization. Today, the Center for Spirituality and Enlightenment is operating in the Republic, and in the implementation of the state policy on youth, its task is to comprehensively explain the essence of the complex geopolitical and ideological-ideological processes taking place in the world, terrorism, religious extremism, fanaticism, separatism, human trafficking. , effective ideological struggle against "popular culture", drug business and other threats is defined.

Practical recommendations.

1. In the process of education and upbringing, it is appropriate to pay attention not only to the improvement of knowledge, skills, and abilities of a person, but also to the formation and development of assertiveness in him. For this purpose, it is necessary to carry out measures aimed at developing critical thinking, reflection and assertiveness, to research the means and methods of psychological manipulation and to eliminate its effects, and to give importance to the formation of necessary skills in young people.

2. Due to the characteristics of adolescence and youth, the desire for active communication and the development of interpersonal relations is a characteristic of young people. From this point of view, everyday communication, behavior and related problems and their solutions, personal attitude, complexity of communication, confusion, stereotypes related to human perception and subjective opinion, issues of the influence of worldview on communication are constantly discussed by parents, educators, relevant officials. and officials are encouraged to be the focus of attention.

3. It is known that views and attitudes towards pedagogical and educational behavior are diverse, and psychological manipulation is an objective phenomenon, an integral part of our social life. The best protection against psychological manipulation is to be able to see and feel it, to form the skills of working with information, to acquire the skills of critical perception of information, to introduce young people to various methods and tools used to influence the mind, and to protect them from the influence of destructive ideas. should be one of the main issues.

REFERENCES

1. Карнеги Д., Карнеги Д. Язык убеждений. – М.: “Эксмо-Пресс”, 2005. Шостром Э. Анти – Карнеги. – Минск: «Полифакт», 1992.
2. Маслоу А. Новые рубежи человеческой природы. – М.: «Альпина нон-фикшн», 2011.
3. Қодиров У.Д. Ёшларни деструктив таъсирлардан химоялашнинг психологик жиҳатлари. Монография, “Фан ва технологиялар” нашриёти, Тошкент, 2013, 236 бет.
4. Вагин И.Г. Уроки психологической защиты. – СПб.: “Питер”, 2001.
5. Козлов Н.И. Истинная правда, или учебник для психолога по жизни. – М.: “АСТПресс”, 2003.

6. Кара-Мурза С.Г. Манипуляция сознанием. – М.: “Эксмо”, 2007.
7. Михайлов Л.А., Соломин В.П., Маликова Т.В., Шатрова О.В. Психологическая безопасность. Учебное пособие. - М.: “Дрофа”, 2008.
8. Ўзбекистонда амалий психологиянинг бугунги ҳолати ва ривожланиш истиқболлари йўналишидаги // Республика илмий-амалий конференция материаллари тўплами. – Т., 2008.
9. Самаров Р.С. Сиёсий психология: ўқув қўлланма. – Т.: “Университет”, 2008.
10. Ташанов А. Бузғунчи ғояларнинг миллий ўзликни англашга салбий таъсири. Фалсафа фанлари бўйича фалсафа доктори (Phd) диссертацияси автореферати. – Т., 2017.
11. Шейнов В.П. Скрытое управление человеком. – М.: “АСТ-пресс”, 2002.